

STAY WITH US AND SUCCESS FOLLOWS: STRATEGIES USED BY ICCBI ADMINISTRATORS TOWARDS EMPLOYEE RETENTION

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Abstract

This study explores the employee retention strategies implemented by administrators in educational institutions, focusing on Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. The qualitative case study involved 10 participants, including administrators and employees selected based on stable tenure and appropriate qualifications. Through face-to-face interviews, key determinants influencing retention, such as teacher satisfaction, job contentment, professional growth, and loyalty, were identified. Recognition and incentives emerged as the primary retention strategy, significantly influencing employee satisfaction and fostering a sense of belonging. The study concludes that these strategies are effective, contributing to the retention of skilled professionals. Recommendations emphasize the importance of recognizing and providing incentives as core strategies for administrators in educational settings, recognizing their role in creating a positive work environment and promoting sustained employee commitment. The findings at ICCBI underscore the observed effectiveness of these strategies.

Keywords: *Employee retention, Strategies, Administrators, Employees*

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Introduction

Expanding on the trend of private school teachers increasingly shifting towards public schools, a collaborative effort between the Department of Education (DepEd) and educators was instrumental in aiming to protect their welfare and rights. This shift gained momentum in 2019 when DepEd-affiliated educators started benefiting from enhanced legal provisions, a change that swiftly prompted their migration. Tibay and Malipot (2018) noted this transition not only in basic education but also extended into higher education, a trend officially acknowledged by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). The surge in new faculty positions within state universities, colleges, and DepEd significantly propelled this shift, reflecting a broader transformation aimed at improving working conditions and opportunities for educators.

When taking a broader perspective, it was evident that most employees tended to seek new opportunities when they felt disengaged at work. This lack of engagement is often translated into reduced motivation and a disconnect from the industry. Career advancement opportunities significantly impacted professionals' decisions to switch jobs, as they aimed for continuous growth. Moreover, being aware of industry standards and market values influenced their perception of worth, including salary considerations. Recognition of their efforts became pivotal; when an industry overlooked their achievements, employees explored new avenues to find appreciation, often in the form of new employment. In essence, fundamental concepts like fairness and transparency wield substantial influence on employees.

In the dynamic professional landscape, employee engagement stands as a key determinant of job satisfaction and overall productivity. Disengagement prompted individuals to seek new opportunities, driven by aspirations for career growth, fair compensation, and acknowledgment of their contributions. In addition, employee retention, a critical organizational strategy, became paramount to fostering growth and preventing productivity losses. High retention rates are correlated with increased employee engagement and efficiency, as highlighted by BasuMallick (2021), who defined employee retention as the deliberate effort to encourage employees to stay with their current company.

Retaining employees was an essential element of the organization's success. It enhanced the educational system of the institution because long-term personnel had more time to polish their talents and complete their responsibilities. The longer individuals stayed in organizations, it helped them develop a greater sense of purpose and confidence in their abilities. An outstanding educational system could boost an institution's credibility, which would lead to the institution's success. Within the context of education, employee retention took on added significance, contributing to the overall success of an institution.

The prolonged tenure of staff allowed for the refinement of skills and the fulfillment of responsibilities, ultimately enhancing the educational system. This was particularly evident in institutions like Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., a Catholic school under the Congregation of Augustinian Recollect (AR) in the Philippines. Despite the availability of alternative opportunities, educators at this institution chose to stay, contributing to its reputation as an excellent AR school.

Catholic schools, such as Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., served as evangelizing communities, fostering integral formation and emphasizing ethical, social, and religious education. This aligned with the broader goal of Catholic education, which sought to mold students into individuals who, equipped with both international standards and Gospel teachings, became agents of positive change in their families and societies (Tabora, 2014).

This study aimed to fill a gap in the existing literature, which tended to focus more on employee turnover than the strategies that encouraged employees to remain within an organization. Also, there were limited studies that showed how employees had retention or what they did to keep their employees in AR and private schools. Supported by the studies of Martson (2014) and Cleef (2022), which stated that retention was a global concern reflected in the Philippines, the crucial need for strategies to retain talented educators amidst high turnover rates was emphasized. Specifically, it explored the retention strategies employed by AR school administrators and the factors that influenced employees' decisions to stay despite possessing qualifications that opened doors to alternative opportunities.

The researchers also investigated the implementation and effectiveness of current retention strategies and offered an Employee Retention Enhancement Program (EREP) for AR schools or private educational institutions facing challenges in employee retention. Through this exploration, the study sought to contribute valuable insights to the broader conversation on employee retention in educational settings.

Statement of the Problems

This study seeks to explore the diverse employee retention strategies employed by AR administrators and evaluate their effectiveness in retaining employees. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What factors contribute to employees choosing to remain within the Immaculate Conception College Balayan, Inc. (ICCB)?
2. What specific retention strategies are currently in use at ICCBI?
3. How do the implemented strategies influence employee retention within the organization?
4. What employee retention enhancement program "EREP" can be formulated for other AR schools or private educational institutions experiencing low employee retention rates?

Methodology

To achieve the study's goal of exploring employee retention strategies employed by AR administrators and assessing their effectiveness, a qualitative research method was chosen, specifically a single case study design focusing on Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. This approach facilitated a thorough examination of retention strategies, including educational programs and events within the organization (Mangarin, 2023). Qualitative research aims to understand employee perspectives and experiences without relying on numerical data. By employing this method, the study aimed to comprehensively explore the diverse strategies utilized by AR administrators at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., shedding light on their contextual effectiveness in retaining employees.

Population and Sampling

The participants in this study included four (4) administrators and six (6) teachers, totaling ten (10) individuals from Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. Participants were selected using purposeful/purposive sampling with criteria-based methods. The ten (10) participants engaged in the pre-survey and interview phases based on specific criteria. Administrators were included if they had more than five (5) years of service in their roles without a school transfer. Similarly, teachers were eligible if they had more than five (5) years of teaching experience, were licensed, and had not undergone a school transfer.

Instrumentations

For data collection in this study, the researchers employed semi-structured interviews as research instruments, recognizing their effectiveness in gathering reliable and comparable qualitative data from multiple participants. The semi-structured interviews consisted of four parts: the first part focused on exploring the factors contributing to employees choosing to remain within Immaculate Conception College Balayan, Inc.; the second part delved into the specific retention strategies currently in use at ICCBI; the third part centered around understanding how these implemented strategies influenced employee retention within the organization; and the last part revolved around formulating an Employee Retention Enhancement Program (EREP) for other AR schools or private educational institutions experiencing low employee retention rates.

Data Collection

The researchers first obtained permission to conduct the study at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., by seeking approval from the school's administrators. After securing permission, they sought additional approval to conduct pre-surveys and interviews. Subsequently, with all necessary approvals, the researchers conducted pre-surveys and face-to-face interviews with school administrators and teachers. The data collected from these participants was then analyzed using thematic analysis, enabling them to compile and interpret the diverse experiences, viewpoints, and actions of the individuals involved.

Data Analysis

The researchers employed a six-step thematic analysis process, following the guidelines suggested by Caulfield, J. (2019), to understand the collected data. They initiated the process by studying the data to gain a profound understanding. Subsequently, they organized data segments based on emerging patterns, identifying connections within the data to create initial themes. Following this, they reviewed the themes to ensure accuracy, refining them for clarity. Each theme was given clear definitions and labels. Finally, the researchers presented their findings clearly, combining themes and providing interpretations. This structured approach enhanced the validity and reliability of the study's findings.

Ethical Considerations

Participants were first clearly informed about interview and pre-survey procedures. The objectives and use of findings were communicated to empower informed decision-making for participation. Informed consent aimed at

equipping participants with the necessary information for conscious involvement. To ensure confidentiality, reports and materials derived from the study avoided sensitive, identifiable information, maintaining utmost participant privacy. Inquiries focused solely on relevant elements, striking a balance of relevance and discretion. Participation was entirely voluntary, allowing participants to withdraw without adverse consequences. No justifications were required, emphasizing a respectful and participant-centric approach throughout the research process.

Results and Discussions

The responses from the 10 participants yielded valuable insights and trends, revealing significant findings across various aspects of the study. Through thorough data analysis, several key themes emerged, shedding light on factors contributing to employee retention at Immaculate Conception College Balayan, Inc. (ICCB), the existing retention strategies at ICCBI, and the influence of these strategies on employee retention within the school.

Table 1

Key Determinants Influencing Employee Retention at Immaculate Conception College Balayan, Inc. (ICCB)

Major Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction	Healthy Work-Life Balance	-P1, P4: Positive work-life balance as a reason for staying -P1, P4: Ability to balance personal life with work commitments -P1: Satisfaction with personal life despite a hectic schedule
	Teacher Satisfaction and Happiness	-P2: Teacher satisfaction and happiness as a contributing factor -P2: The positive attitude of teachers at ICCBI -P3, P4, P5: Collegial support and camaraderie among teachers -P3: Forgiveness and understanding among colleagues
	Job Satisfaction	-P3: Sense of being an asset to the institution -P4, P5: Feeling secure and stable in the organization -P5: Positive outlook on the opportunity's stability -P6: Contentment with the job and salary
Professional Development and Opportunities	Professional Growth Opportunities	-P1, P2: Opportunities for attending seminars and workshops -P3: Incentives for post-graduate studies and research -P4, P6: Training, seminars, and career enrichment -P5: Opportunities in the professional learning community
	Support from Administration	-P2, P5: Administration's support for professional growth -P3, P6: Communication and responsiveness of administration -P6: Fulfilling specific requests made to the administration
Collegial Relationships and Sense of Belonging Appreciation and Loyalty	Camaraderie and Relationships	-P4, P5: Sense of camaraderie among colleagues -P3: Support and understanding from officemates -P6: Strong relationships and a sense of belonging
	Gratitude and Loyalty	-P4: Loyalty and gratitude towards colleagues and the institution -P6: Deep appreciation for the opportunities provided by ICCBI -P3, P5: Recognition of kindness and support from colleagues and leadership -P6: Building a career and a sense of family at ICCBI

The data above outlines the crucial factors influencing employee retention at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., presenting four major themes along with their respective sub-themes and codes.

The primary theme explores the realms of work-life balance and job satisfaction, emphasizing the paramount importance of striking a harmonious equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal contentment in one's role. In the contemporary workplace, employees actively seek environments that facilitate a seamless integration of work obligations and personal life, departing from settings that enforce one at the expense of the other, as highlighted by Gorde (2019).

Within this overarching theme, three (3) sub-themes emerge, collectively encompassing eleven (11) codes. The first sub-theme revolves around fostering a healthy work-life balance, wherein individuals adeptly manage their professional responsibilities and personal lives. This approach ensures dedicated time and attention to both work commitments and personal pursuits, ultimately resulting in reduced stress, enhanced well-being, and an overall improved quality of life, a sentiment shared by P1, "I would say that I have a healthy work-life balance because, despite my hectic schedule, I still have time for my personal life."

In addition, teacher satisfaction and happiness, another sub-theme that was discovered under this theme, represent the level of contentment, fulfillment, and positive emotional well-being experienced by educators within their role, often influenced by factors such as job appreciation, supportive work environments, opportunities for growth, meaningful connections with students, and a sense of accomplishment in their teaching endeavors. According to P3, "Most of them are my age; we started the teaching force in SHS together. They are very forgiving and understanding. I always find allowances for my mistakes from them; of course, they are very generous. They are one of the reasons I stay."

This sentiment was supported by "I perceive a sense of camaraderie because we frequently exchanged experiences, problems, etc." and by the statement saying, "We all treat each other as brothers and sisters, and we are all open to each other."

While job satisfaction, or the individual's overall contentment, fulfillment, and positive feelings towards their job or work environment, is the last sub-theme under work-life balance and job satisfaction, as stated by P3, "I've worked hard to excel in the subjects I teach, so I guess I've become an asset to the institution (I hope)."

Supported by the statement saying, "I feel secure in the organization. I've been here for 16 years." And it was also supported, as stated by the participant, saying "the opportunity is stable." And P6 also stated that "I find my job fulfilling, and I'm content with my salary."

The subsequent major theme identified is professional development and opportunities. Arora (2023) elucidates that organizations investing in employee development empower their workforce to refine existing skills and gain new competencies, effectively preparing them for their roles. Recognizing the intrinsic link between growth and an

individual's career trajectory, it becomes crucial for employees to perceive a clear path for their professional advancement within their current organization. As highlighted by Gorde (2019), when employees cannot visualize their career progression within a company, they are more likely to seek opportunities elsewhere at the earliest chance.

Within this theme, two (2) sub-themes emerge. The first sub-theme (1) is professional growth opportunities, encompassing various chances and avenues provided by organizations for employees to enhance their skills, knowledge, and expertise within their field or industry. These opportunities may include training programs, workshops, certifications, mentorship, and defined career advancement paths. As articulated by P1, "Some of the things that the school offers are the opportunity to attend seminars and workshops related to your profession and expertise.

It was supported, "especially in terms of research, with the institution. I am inspired to conduct my own study. I chaired a research defense and advised research groups, which expanded my career opportunities. We are also encouraged to take further postgraduate studies; incentives even so will help." This is also supported by the statement, "The school provides us with training and seminars that we can use in our professional growth."

Moreover, "There are many opportunities waiting outside—more engagement in the professional learning community."

While the last sub-theme under this major theme is support from the administration, assistance, or backing provided by the administrative body within an organization, according to P6, "At ICC, numerous opportunities for career growth, such as seminars and training sessions, have enriched my professional development. Exploring various towns and countries has not only been enjoyable but also a source of valuable learning experiences."

Then, the third major theme revolves around collegial relationships and fostering a sense of belonging. Retaining key team members often correlates with sustained long-term success. Carr et al. (2019) emphasize that when employees feel a strong sense of belonging, organizations can gain substantial financial advantages. Notably, workers who experience a heightened sense of belonging demonstrate a 167% increase in their employer promoter score, indicating a greater inclination to recommend their company to others.

Within this major theme, one (1) sub-theme emerges: camaraderie and relationships, highlighting mutual support and strong interpersonal connections among individuals within a group, team, or organization. This fosters a positive and cohesive atmosphere, as shared by P4, "I perceive a sense of camaraderie because we frequently exchange experiences and problems."

It is supported by a statement saying that "they are very forgiving and understanding. I always find allowances for my mistakes from them; of course, they are very generous." It is also supported by the statement saying, "They are like a second family to me, and ICC feels like my second home."

The final major theme centers on appreciation and loyalty towards the organization and its colleagues. Arqawi et al. (2018) note that an employee's commitment to staying with a company often hinges on their perception of robust organizational support. This support fosters positive engagement, encouraging active contributions not only to procedural implementation but also to goal-setting, planning, and the formulation of overarching company policies. In this major theme, there is one (1) sub-theme named Gratitude and Loyalty, which is the feelings of appreciation, dedication, and commitment individuals hold towards their organization, colleagues, or work environment, acknowledging the value, support, and opportunities provided while fostering a deep sense of loyalty and attachment towards the shared goals and ethos of the workplace. According to P4, "An ICCnian is an ICCnian forever."

It is supported by the statement saying that "I find my job fulfilling, and I'm content with my salary. I also cherish the opportunities for travel. Most importantly, ICC has guided me to strengthen my relationship with God." And "ICC has provided me with a career I never thought possible. I hold great affection for the people here, both the students and my colleagues."

It is also supported by the statement of P3, "I think the people (my officemates) really, and the "utang naloob" I owe to my ---, like Ma'am Nalyn, for accepting me as a teacher when I was still arguably very unqualified."

Table 2

The retention strategies implemented by the school administration at ICCBI

Major Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Communication and Engagement	Orientation and Reorientation	-P8: Orientation for new employees -P8: Clear role expectations
	Information Dissemination	-P9: Communication through academic, co-curricular, and administrative offices -P10: Meetings and personal communication
	Open Communication	-P7: Open communication with administrators -P8: Unrestricted line of communication
	Employee Engagement Activities	-P9: Employee engagement activities, educational tours, recollections, and team building -P7: Up skilling and professional development
Recognition and Incentives	Recognition and Rewards	-P10: Recognition and benefits -P7: Incentives and professional development -P8: Non-monetary forms of recognition and appreciation -P8: Regular retention strategies
	Career Advancement	-P8: Promotions and career growth -P8: Ranking system for potential employees
Feedback and Evaluation	Evaluation and Feedback	-P7: Evaluation through individual conferences -P9: Checklists and surveys
	Adaptation to Needs	-P9: Strategies based on prioritized needs and expectations -P10: Needed for accreditation

As detailed in this table, administrators' perspectives on their implemented retention strategies include corresponding sub-themes and codes derived from participant data. The primary theme is "Communication and Engagement," which involves information exchange and active participation. Emphasizing the significance of personalizing interactions with staff, recognizing the social nature of individuals, and cultivating a sense of connection enhances the potential for individuals to realize their fullest capabilities. This, in turn, nurtures feelings of appreciation and connection that extend beyond the confines of the classroom (Joseph, M.X., 2022). The primary theme is further broken down into four (4) sub-themes and eight (8) codes.

The first sub-theme under this major theme is orientation and reorientation. The orientation introduces new employees to the company's culture and role, while the reorientation refreshes existing employees' skills to adapt to changes within the organization, both ensuring alignment with evolving company dynamics and objectives, according to P8.

In addition, information dissemination is another sub-theme that was discovered under this major theme, which involves the strategic sharing of relevant information, policies, updates, and key insights among employees, stakeholders, or departments within it, according to P9.

Another sub-theme that the major theme has is open communication, which involves transparent and unrestricted sharing of information, ideas, and feedback among all members, fostering trust, collaboration, and a conducive environment for effective teamwork. According to this, it is practiced "through open communication with the administrators" (P7).

Employee engagement activities encompass diverse programs and initiatives designed to involve and motivate employees, foster a positive work environment, and enhance productivity. It is another sub-theme discovered by the researchers under this major theme.

While the second major theme involves "Recognition and Incentives" (P, B. 2013), it highlights that acknowledgment positively impacts individuals by boosting self-esteem, confidence, and enthusiasm for innovation. Meanwhile, reward systems are designed to attract and retain committed individuals, inspiring heightened performance within the organization.

The first sub-theme under this major theme is recognition and rewards, which refer to acknowledging and incentivizing employees for their contributions, achievements, or exceptional performance within an organization through various means such as bonuses, awards, praise, promotions, or additional responsibilities, aiming to boost morale, motivation, and retention while reinforcing positive behaviors and outcomes.

While career advancement, or the progression and development of an individual's career within an organization or profession, often involving promotions, increased responsibilities, skill development, further education,

or opportunities for higher-level roles, aims to enhance one's professional growth, skills, and status within their field, is another sub-theme under this major theme.

The third major sub-theme centers on "feedback and evaluation," as stated by 15Five, D. H. C. O. (2021), managers providing structured feedback enhance employee performance. Moreover, high-performing employees value continuous opportunities to improve work efficiency, thriving in environments that encourage giving and receiving constructive feedback.

The first sub-theme that was developed by the researchers is evaluation and feedback, as shared by the administrators: "The administrators make it possible through evaluation or individual conferences" (P) and "through checklists and surveys" (P9).

Another sub-theme is feedback and evaluation, where adaptation to needs is the ability to adjust, modify, or tailor strategies, products, services, or approaches to meet specific or changing requirements, circumstances, or demands, ensuring relevance, effectiveness, and suitability in addressing identified needs or challenges. As shared by the participants, they stated that "our administration bases the strategies on prioritized needs and expectations" (P9). While it is supported by the statement of P10 saying that "it is needed for the ongoing accreditation."

Table 3

Influence of the implemented strategies on employee retention within the ICCBI

Major Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Organizational Culture and Sense of Belonging	Sense of Family and Belonging	-P7: ICCnian spirit and family -P7, P8: Harmonious relationships -P7, P8: Feeling of belongingness -P7: Inclusivity
	Positive Work Environment	-P8, P9: Positive work environment
Employee Inspiration and Development	Employee Well-Being Employee Motivation	-P9: Employee wellness -P10: Employee inspiration
Measurable Outcomes and Success Indicators	Retention Success	-P7, P8: Employee retention
	Feedback and Validation	-P9: Feedback and validation

In Table 3, the researchers outline the "Influence of Implemented Strategies on Employee Retention" at ICCBI, highlighting three major themes along with their corresponding sub-themes and codes.

The initial major theme revolves around "Organizational Culture and Sense of Belonging." According to Carr et al. (2019), fostering a sense of belonging among employees leads to significant financial advantages for organizations. In addition, it developed two (2) sub-themes and five (5) codes. Sub-theme number one (1) is the sense of family and belonging to fostering an environment where individuals feel emotionally connected, supported, and

valued, akin to being part of a cohesive and caring family unit, creating a strong bond, trust, and shared identity among employees.

Participants emphasized the significance of the ICCnian spirit and family atmosphere, which foster inclusivity and a harmonious relationship among employees, promoting a sense of belonging and unity within ICCBI.

Another sub-theme, a positive work environment, underscores the importance of a supportive, respectful, and collaborative workplace culture that enhances employee satisfaction and productivity.

The second major theme delves into "Employee Inspiration Development." Mulang (2021) highlights that a motivated teacher is more inclined to actively pursue goals and fulfill tasks promptly. This theme emphasizes how fostering motivation among employees can positively impact their dedication and efficiency in task completion. The major theme has two (2) sub-themes and two (2) codes.

The number one (1) subtheme, employee well-being, focuses on promoting holistic health, satisfaction, and fulfillment of individuals within the workplace, fostering a supportive environment that promotes work-life balance, safety, health, and personal development.

Employee motivation, the second sub-theme, highlights the importance of intrinsic and extrinsic factors in driving employees to invest their energy and commitment toward achieving organizational goals.

The third major theme, "Measurable Outcomes and Success Indicators," underscores the significance of a robust organizational culture in employee retention, as noted by Gorde (2019). This theme highlights how a strong organizational culture significantly contributes to employees' contentment and reduces their inclination to seek alternative job opportunities. It has two (2) sub-themes and two (2) codes.

The first sub-theme, retention success, emphasizes the effectiveness of strategies, policies, and workplace environments in promoting job satisfaction, engagement, professional growth, and a positive work culture, ultimately reducing turnover and retaining valuable talent within the organization.

Participants noted measurable outcomes of success, such as employee retention rates and feedback, indicating the effectiveness of retention strategies implemented by ICCBI.

Overall, the findings underscore the importance of organizational culture, employee well-being, motivation, and measurable outcomes in enhancing employee retention at ICCBI

EMPLOYEE RETENTION ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM "EREP"

Specific Area	Strategies	Objectives	Month	Person Involved	Budget
Key Determinants Influencing Employee Retention	- Enhance teacher satisfaction and happiness	- Improve overall job satisfaction	Ongoing	Human Resources Department	TBD
	- Facilitate professional growth opportunities	- Foster a positive work environment	Ongoing	Department Heads, Administrators	TBD
	- Implement gratitude and loyalty programs	- Strengthen employee loyalty and commitment	Ongoing	Employee Engagement Committee	TBD
	- Promote work-life balance	- Encourage a healthy work-life balance	Ongoing	Administration and HR Department	TBD
Retention Strategies Implemented by the Administration	- Enhance recognition and rewards programs	- Acknowledge and reward outstanding contributions	Ongoing	Human Resources Department	TBD
	- Conduct regular orientation and re-orientation sessions	- Ensure employees are well-informed and engaged	Ongoing	Training and Development Team	TBD
	- Improve information dissemination	- Enhance communication within the organization	Ongoing	Communication Department	TBD
	- Foster open communication	- Promote transparency and a collaborative culture	Ongoing	Leadership Team, Communication Dept.	TBD
	- Organize employee engagement activities	- Boost morale and team cohesion	Monthly	Employee Engagement Committee	TBD
	- Support career advancement opportunities	- Facilitate professional growth and development	Ongoing	Department Heads, Administrators	TBD
	- Establish regular evaluation and feedback mechanisms	- Provide constructive feedback for improvement	Quarterly	Human Resources Department	TBD
	- Adaptation to individual needs	- Customize support based on employee requirements	Ongoing	HR Department, Employee Support Team	TBD
	- Cultivate a sense of family and belonging	- Enhance organizational culture and cohesion	Ongoing	Leadership Team, Employee Support Team	TBD
	- Foster a positive work environment	- Promote employee well-being and satisfaction	Ongoing	Administration and HR Department	TBD
Influence of Implemented Strategies on Employee Retention	- Motivate employees through recognition and rewards	- Boost morale and job satisfaction	Ongoing	Employee Engagement Committee	TBD
	- Prioritize employee well-being	- Ensure a healthy and supportive work environment	Ongoing	Employee Support Team, HR Department	TBD
	- Ensure retention success through targeted initiatives	- Track and celebrate successful retention outcomes	Ongoing	Leadership Team, HR Department	TBD
	- Provide regular feedback and validation	- Recognize and validate employee contributions	Quarterly	Human Resources Department	TBD

Table 4

Employee Retention Enhancement Program "EREP"

The "Employee Retention Enhancement Program" (EREP) is a meticulously crafted strategic initiative designed to fortify and enhance employee retention within AR schools or private educational institutions. This initiative is particularly informed by the challenges identified in the gathered data from Immaculate Conception College Balayan, Inc. (ICCBI).

EREP takes a purposeful approach, identifying and intervening in key areas crucial to employee retention. Its comprehensive strategies encompass a spectrum of initiatives, ranging from enhancing job satisfaction and fostering a positive work environment to implementing recognition and reward systems, supporting professional growth, and ensuring a healthy work-life balance.

The program is meticulously structured, establishing clear and measurable objectives for each strategy and implementing an ongoing timeline for both implementation and assessment. To ensure accountability and a coordinated organizational effort, specific individuals and departments are assigned responsibility for each aspect of the program.

EREP goes beyond strategic planning by allocating resources, both in terms of budget and personnel. Emphasizing the importance of continuous monitoring, feedback mechanisms, and adaptability to individual needs, the program is designed to evolve with the dynamic nature of employee requirements.

Ultimately, EREP adopts a holistic approach to address both intrinsic and extrinsic factors influencing employee retention. The program aims to cultivate a workplace culture where employees feel valued, supported, and motivated, fostering sustained commitment to the organization.

Conclusions

This single-case qualitative research delves into the strategies employed by administrators at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. (ICCBI) to retain their employees. Thematic analysis, comprising familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing them up, provided a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing employee retention.

The findings, presented in Tables 1, 2, and 3, shed light on the influential factors that contribute to every employee's decision to stay at ICCBI. Noteworthy elements include high levels of teacher satisfaction and happiness, job satisfaction, abundant professional growth opportunities, and a prevailing sense of gratitude and loyalty. These factors collectively create an environment where employees find fulfillment and contentment in their roles, fostering a strong bond with the organization.

Table 2 underscores the importance of "recognition and rewards" as a consistent and effective strategy for administrators aiming to retain their employees. In addition to this, the utilization of orientation and re-orientation,

information dissemination, open communication, employee engagement activities, career advancement, evaluation and feedback, and adaptation to needs further reinforces the administrators' commitment to ensuring employee satisfaction and retention.

Table 3 provides insight into the broader impact of these strategies. It concludes that the implemented techniques not only contribute to employee retention but also foster a sense of family and belonging within the organization. The strategies employed by administrators at ICCBI extend beyond mere retention; they create an organizational culture where employees feel valued, supported, and connected, further solidifying their commitment to the institution.

Overall, the study emphasizes the multifaceted nature of effective retention strategies, highlighting the interplay between various factors that contribute to a positive and enduring employer-employee relationship.

Recommendations

In the competitive landscape of private education, where skilled educators and staff are integral to success, AR school administrators face unique challenges in retaining talent. To navigate these challenges, several recommendations are proposed. First and foremost, administrators should prioritize strategies that promote a healthy work-life balance, recognizing its impact on employee satisfaction and retention. Additionally, ensuring fairness in workload distribution among teachers fosters a supportive and collaborative work environment.

Another crucial aspect for AR school administrators is benchmarking with other institutions to gather insights into enhancing operational effectiveness. Exploring benchmarking initiatives with other AR schools and private institutions can provide valuable perspectives. Moreover, administrators should consider aligning pay rates with those of public-school teachers to remain competitive, all while maintaining a focus on quality spending.

Recognizing the pivotal role of HR in talent management, administrators are advised to invest in HR professionals. Streamlining employee management processes and emphasizing the importance of HR in fostering retention and organizational effectiveness contribute significantly to the overall success of an educational institution.

Future HR professionals play a critical role in shaping organizational culture and driving employee engagement. To prepare for this role, individuals pursuing HR careers should focus on cultivating comprehensive skills in recruitment and management. An emphasis on understanding and aligning with organizational culture during the hiring process fosters harmony and promotes shared objectives crucial for success.

Encouraging researchers to explore retention strategies in public schools, with a specific focus on retaining highly skilled teachers amidst budget constraints and competition, is essential. The insights gained from these comparative investigations can inform HR practices and policy decisions, fostering organizational improvement and enhancing overall employee retention and effectiveness.

Lastly, fostering collaborative efforts between HR professionals and researchers is vital to address the dynamic needs of the education sector. Such collaboration ensures a holistic approach to talent management, driving sustainable success and growth for educational institutions. By embracing these recommendations, AR school administrators can navigate challenges effectively and create environments that foster continuous growth among employee.

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